

Self regulation of tamil linguistic minority students in relation to their home environment

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Abstract:

Human beings possess a highly adaptive quality known as self-regulation, which assists learners in planning, organizing tasks, setting goals, and self-evaluating throughout task completion. This attribute is closely related to different learning contexts guided by the home environment. The current study examined the home environment's impact on the self-regulation of 9th-grade students. The study involved 350 students from Tamil medium secondary schools in Palakkad. Using home environment inventory and a self-regulated learning scale, the study assessed home environment and the level of self-regulation among students. Correlational and regression analysis was employed to examine the relationship between the home environment and self-regulation. The relationship between self regulation and home environment for the Total sample is found to be having negligible correlation. That is, there exists no significant relationship between self regulation and home environment for the Total sample.

Keywords: Home environment, Self regulation, Tamil linguistic minority students.

Introduction:

The academic achievements and overall development of students are affected by different factors, and a determinant is the home environment they experience. This holds particular significance for Tamil linguistic minority students, influencing their linguistic, cultural, social, and academic progress. As described by Zimmerman (2000), self-regulation involves "self-generated thoughts, feelings, and actions that are planned and cyclically adapted to the attainment of personal goals." The relationship between the home environment and self-regulation encompasses various factors. Self-Regulation Theory elucidates the complexities of determining thoughts, feelings, speech, and actions for optimal decision-making. Critical to making informed choices, its components include standards of desirable behavior, motivation, monitoring, and willpower, all interacting dynamically in self-regulatory processes. Kadiravan (2012) emphasized that a positive home environment and quality early child education contribute to the development of self-regulation skills. Socio-economic

challenges and limited parental involvement may hinder self-regulation development among Tamil linguistic minority students.

Different dimensions, such as executive functions, delay of gratification, cognitive or inhibitory control, motor control, sustained attention, and working memory, serve as indications to evaluate children's self-regulation (Baumeister & Vohs, 2004). These dimensions consist of behaviors in self-regulation, with executive functions being central to the intent of self-regulation (Baumeister & Vohs, 2004). The earliest signs of self-regulation begin in infancy, with regulatory skills growing in toddlers and progressing towards more internal control as children age. Cummins (2000) emphasizes the role of the home: "The most effective support for language minority students is that which is integrated into the home environment." Home environments are not uniform, and socio-economic factors can significantly influence educational dynamics. Understanding how these conditions intersect with self-regulation is essential in fostering an inclusive academic environment.

As Gloria Ladson-Billings (1998) noted, "Identity is never just a single, exclusive category; it's always a complex and fluid construct." By knowing how cultural practices, language use, parental engagement, and socio-economic factors influence self-regulation skills is crucial for designing effective interventions and support systems. Albert Bandura's social cognitive theory becomes particularly relevant in examining how self-regulation is acquired. Bandura (1986) notes, "Learning would be exceedingly laborious, not to mention hazardous if people had to rely solely on the effects of their own actions to inform them what to do." Integrating culturally relevant content and practices into the curriculum can provide a meaningful connection between students' backgrounds and the educational material, fostering a sense of relevance and applicability.

Review of Related Studies:

Anyichie et al. (2023) examined classroom contexts that support the engagement of culturally diverse learners through the integration of self-regulated learning practices (SRLPPs) and culturally responsive pedagogical practices (CRPPs). The study involved two elementary school teachers and 43 students from Grades 4 and 5. A multiple, parallel case study design incorporating mixed methods was used to analyze how teachers embedded SRLPPs and CRPPs within complex learning tasks, how culturally diverse students participated in these tasks, and how students' engagement experiences were connected to instructional practices. The findings indicated that teachers effectively utilized the culturally responsive self-regulated learning (CR-SRL) framework in designing complex tasks. The inclusion of these practices enhanced student engagement, and learner–context interactions showed that engagement depended on specific task features present on a given day.

Russell et al. (2022) investigated instructional practices, beliefs, and experiences of educators that support the development of self-regulated learning in higher education across multiple disciplines. Data collected through questionnaires and semi-structured interviews were analyzed to identify key instructional approaches. The results emphasized four categories of teaching strategies used to promote self-regulated learning. The study also outlined the conditions that enable educators to support student self-regulation and identified challenges encountered during implementation.

Kaur (2019) conducted a study titled “A Study of Academic Stress and Academic Achievement among Adolescents of Economically Weaker Sections in Relation to Family Climate and School Environment”. Using multistage random sampling, 600 eleventh-grade students were selected from government senior secondary schools in Punjab. The results revealed a significant negative relationship between family climate and academic stress. It suggests that a supportive family environment is associated with lower levels of academic stress among secondary school students.

Objectives of the Study:

- To find out the levels of Self regulation among Tamil linguistic minority students of Kerala
- To find out the levels of home environment among Tamil linguistic minority students of Kerala
- To find out whether there exists any significant relationship between self regulation and home environment among Tamil linguistic minority students for the Total sample.

Hypotheses of the Study:

- Self regulation may vary among Tamil linguistic minority students of Kerala
- Home environment may vary among Tamil linguistic minority students of Kerala
- There exists a significant relationship between self regulation and home environment among Tamil linguistic minority students for the Total Sample.

Methodology of the Study:

The method adopted for this study was the Survey method. The sample for this study consists of 350 Tamil linguistic minority students from various tamil medium schools of Palakkad district giving due representation based on Simple random sampling technique. Self Regulation Questionnaire (Developed and standardized by Brown, Miller & Lawendowski, 1999): Self Regulation Questionnaire is a self report inventory designed to assess self-regulatory processes. It consists of 63 items to be answered on a Likert scale ranging from 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 9 (Strongly Agree). Home environment scale (Developed and standardized by Manjuvani, 1989): The inventory consists of 78 statements and it was subdivided into part-A and part-B. Part-A consists of 66 statements and

the statements are subdivided into ten dimensions designed with three-point scale (many times, sometimes and rarely). Part A items related to perceived psycho-social environment. Part-B consists of 36 statements (12 items; divided into three categories: (availability, opportunity and utilization). Part-B deals with the physical aspects of the home environment. Percentage analysis, t- test and Karl Person's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation.

Results and Interpretation:

Levels of Self regulation and home environment among Tamil linguistic minority students:

Levels of Self regulation and home environment among Tamil linguistic minority students were found out by classifying them into three groups namely High, Average and Low based on their score of Self regulation and home environment.

Figure 1.

Pie diagram showing levels of Self regulation among Tamil linguistic minority students for the Total Sample

When the scores of Self-regulation of Tamil linguistic minority students were assessed, it was found that 10% of Tamil linguistic minority students possess High Self regulation, 76% have Average and 20% have Low Self regulation. The results showed that the majority of Tamil linguistic minority students possess an average level of Self regulation.

Figure 2.

Pie diagram showing levels of home environment among Tamil linguistic minority students for the Total Sample

When the scores of home environment of Tamil linguistic minority students were assessed, it was found that 17% of Tamil linguistic minority students possess a high level of home environment, 69% have an Average level, and 19% have a Low level of home environment. The results indicate that the majority of Tamil linguistic minority students possess an average level of home environment.

Relationship between Self regulation and home environment among Tamil linguistic minority students for the Total Sample:

Karl Pearson's product moment coefficient of correlation was used to find out the strength of relationship between Self regulation and home environment of Tamil linguistic minority students and the following findings were obtained for the total sample.

Table 1

The details of relationship between Self regulation and home environment for the Total sample

Variables	Sample	N	Coefficient of Correlation “r”	P value
Self regulation & Home environment	Total Sample	350	0.088	0.191

The results show that the relationship between the two variables is found to have very negligible correlation, but it may not be reflected in the population. That is, there exists no significant relationship between Self regulation and home environment for the Total sample.

Discussion of Results:

The Hypotheses 1 and 2 were tested using Percentage analysis. The results indicated that Self regulation and home environment may vary among Tamil linguistic minority students and were classified as High, Average and Low levels. It was found that 10% of Tamil linguistic minority students possess high Self regulation, 76% have average and 20% have low Self regulation. In the case of home environment, 17% of Tamil linguistic minority students possess high levels of Home environment, 69% have average and 19% have low levels of home environment. Therefore, both hypotheses were fully substantiated. The Hypothesis 3 was tested using Karl Pearson's product moment coefficient of correlation. Here the coefficient of correlation is 0.088 and 'p' value is 0.191. The results show that the relationship between the two variables is found to be having very negligible correlation. That is, there exists no significant relationship between Self regulation and Home environment for the Total sample. Therefore, the hypothesis is fully rejected.

Conclusion:

The scores of Self-regulations and Home environment were assessed, it was found that majority of the Tamil linguistic minority students possess average level of Self regulation and Home environment. The relationship between Self regulation and Home environment for the Total sample is found to be having negligible correlation. That is, there exists no significant relationship between Self regulation and home environment for the Total sample.

Suggestions

- The study may be conducted on large samples for drawing generalization and to get more reliable results.
- Comparative study on the same variables can be done on the basis of students of different levels. Eg. Primary level, secondary level and senior secondary level, undergraduate level.

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